

7. H. E. AUDIER, R. BENGLMANS and B. C. DAS, *Tetrahedron letters*, 1966, 4341.
8. J. BERGMAN, B. O. LINDGREN and C. M. SVAHN, *Acta. Chem. Scand.*, 1965, 19, 1661.
9. E. RITCHIE, R. G. SENIOR and W. C. TAYLOR, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1969, 22, 2371.
10. R. LABRIOLA and G. OURISSON, *Tetrahedron*, 1971, 27, 1901.
11. Y. TACHI, S. TAGA, Y. KAMANO and M. KOMATSU, *Chem. Pharm. Bull. (Japan)*, 1971, 19, 2193.
12. R. SUNDER, K. N. N. AYENGER and S. RANGASWAMI, *J. Chem. Soc. (Perkin-I)*, 1976, 117.
13. P. CRABBE, "Optical rotatory dispersion and Circular Dichroism in Organic Chemistry", Holden-Day, Sanfrancisco 1965, p. 232 and references cited therein.
14. "Topics in Carbon-13 NMR Spectroscopy", Vol. 2 p. 92-105, 1976, Wiley-Interscience, edited by George Levy.

Synthesis of New Schiff's Bases : Terephthalaldehyde Bis (Semicarbazone) and Terephthalaldehyde Bis (4-Phenylthiosemicarbazone)

P. L. MAURYA, B. V. AGARWALA AND ARUN K. DEY*

Chemical Laboratories,
University of Allahabad, Allahabad-211 002.

Manuscript received 17 August 1977, accepted 6 December 1977

THE present communication is in continuation with the work¹⁻³ on coordination polymers in progress in these laboratories and describes the synthesis of bidentate coordinating ligands obtained by the condensation of terephthalaldehyde with semicarbazide or 4-phenylthiosemicarbazide. The reactions are :

(I)

(II)

The composition of compounds TPBS (I) and TPBPTS (II) have been established from elemental analyses data, and the structures elucidated through a study of infrared spectra (table 1).

TABLE 1—INFRA-RED SPECTRA (CM⁻¹) OF TEREPHTHALALDEHYDE BIS (SEMICARBAZONE) AND TEREPHTHALALDEHYDE BIS (4-PHENYLTHIOSEMICARBAZONE)

TPBS	TPBPTS	Band assignments
3540s 3320m	3480m 3340w	N-H stretching
3020w 3000s	3040m	=C-H stretching
2320m	2330m	-C=N absorption of Schiff's base
1685s	1680vs	C=N stretching
1660s	...	C=O stretching
1645s 1640sh	1645s 1640sh	NH ₂ deformation
1590vs 1540s 1500s	1590vs 1550s 1500s	C=C and C=N-N stretching vibrations
1495s 1440vs ...	1480s 1430s 1340vs	C=S and N-C-N stretching C-N stretching of the Ar-N type
1155s 1070vs	1140s 1080s	para-di substituted phenyl ring
920vs 830s 730vs	975s 870s 750vs	C-H out of plane bending vibrations
495vs	450s	N-C-N deformation

s = strong, vs = very sharp, sh = shoulder, w = weak, m = medium

* For correspondence

The formation of Schiff's bases of 1:2 type (aldehyde: carbazide) is indicated from analysis. The presence of an aromatic type structure is recognised⁴ by the presence of =C-H stretching vibrations near 3030 cm^{-1} and C=C vibrations in the region, 1590 to 1500 cm^{-1} . The absorption bands observed near 3440 to 3340 cm^{-1} and 1645 cm^{-1} correspond to N-H stretching and NH_2 deformation, respectively. The strong absorption peak at 1660 cm^{-1} in the spectra of (I) is due to the presence of C=O group and C=S group in (II) is indicated by the peak at 1495 cm^{-1} . The C=N linkage of Schiff's base type⁴ is confirmed by the bands near 2330 cm^{-1} in both the compounds. A very sharp absorption band at 1340 cm^{-1} in the spectra of compound (II) shows the C-N stretching of Ar-N type. The C=N-N and N-C-N type linkages are shown by peaks near 1510 cm^{-1} and 1440 cm^{-1} .⁵

The purity of the compounds were checked by TLC.

Experimental

Materials: Samples of terephthalaldehyde (Koch-Light); semicarbazide hydrochloride and 4-phenylthiosemicarbazide (Fluka), were employed. Solvents used were of reagent grade.

Preparation of terephthalaldehyde bis-(semicarbazone) (TPBS): Semicarbazide hydrochloride, 11.15 g, 0.1 mole was dissolved in 100 ml hot water and 50 ml 1N NaOH solution was added. This solution was mixed with terephthalaldehyde (6.70 g, 0.05 mole dissolved in 100 ml ethanol) gradually with constant stirring. On shaking for a few minutes, a yellow coloured powdery solid separated. The whole mass was then refluxed over a waterbath for 1hr to ensure the completion of the reaction and the solid was filtered, washed with hot water, ethanol, and ether successively, and dried under reduced pressure over calcium chloride; yield 86%. Found: C, 48.06; H, 4.53; N, 32.94; Calc. for $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_2\text{N}_6$; C, 48.32; H, 4.83; N, 33.57%.

The compound is insoluble in water, acetone, ethanol, chloroform, benzene, tetrahydrofuran, but has a little solubility in dimethylformamide and dimethylsulphoxide.

Preparation of terephthalaldehyde bis-(4-phenylthiosemicarbazone), (TPBPTS): 8.35g, 0.05 mole 4-phenylthiosemicarbazide dissolved in 150ml ethanol was added to an ethanolic solution of terephthalaldehyde (3.35g, 0.025 mole dissolved in 50ml ethanol) and the mixture was refluxed over a waterbath for ca 2h. A yellow solid separated, which was left for few hours and filtered, washed with ethanol and ether, and dried under reduced pressure over calcium chloride; yield 84%.

The compound is insoluble in water and other common organic solvents, but highly soluble in dimethylformamide and dimethylsulphoxide. Found: C, 60.67; H, 5.06; N, 19.50; Calc. for $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_6\text{S}_2$; C, 61.10; H, 4.66; N, 19.44%.

Infra-red absorption spectra: The i.r. absorption spectra were recorded with a Beckmann infra-red spectrophotometer in the range of 4000 to 400 cm^{-1} using KBr pellets.

Acknowledgement

The work was carried out under a project of the Ministry of Defence, Government of India and the authors are thankful for the financial support. Elemental analyses and i. r. spectra measurements were done through the courtesy of Professor B. C. Halder, Director, Institute of Science, Bombay, and the authors express their gratitude for the same.

References

1. P. L. MAURYA, B. V. AGARWALA and A. K. DEY, *Inorg. Nucl. Chem. Letters*, 1977, 13, 145.
2. P. L. MAURYA, B. V. AGARWALA and A. K. DEY, *Indian J. Chem.*, (In press).
3. V. BANERJEE and A. K. DEY, *Curr : Sci.*, 1977, 46, 778.
4. L. J. BELLAMY, "The Infra-red Spectra of Complex Molecules". John Wiley, New York 1954, p. 54 & p. 146.
5. K. UENO and A. E. MARTELL, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1955, 59, 998.

Unsaponifiable Matter of *Cordia rothii* Roem & Schult (Fruits)

Y. S. VERMA, V. K. SAXENA* & S. S. NIGAM

Chemistry Department, Saugar University, SAGAR (M.P.)

Manuscript 19 May 1977, revised 14 October 1977,
accepted 16 January 1978

CORDIA rothii Roem & Schult^{1,2,3} (N. O. Boraginaceae, Hindi-Gondi) has fruits of sweetish mucilaginous taste, aromatic agreeable odour and good source of carbohydrates.

Due to its nutritive value it was taken up for phytochemical investigations. The present communication describes the study of the unsaponifiable matter from the fruits.

4 kg. powdered fruits on extraction with petroleum ether (40-60°) in a soxhlet extractor and removal of the solvent under reduced pressure yielded 75 g. of a yellow coloured fatty material. On saponification with 0.5 N KOH it yielded an unsaponifiable matter which was extracted with ether. Removal of ether gave a waxy residue (3.10 g.) which was subjected to column chromatography over 125 g. of alumina. The column was successively eluted with (i) petroleum ether (60-80°), (ii) petroleum ether (60-80°) : benzene (2:1) and (iii) benzene : chloroform (1:1). The three eluates were collected separately and solvent distilled off under reduced pressure. The residue from the eluates (i) on